

Dissemination, Engagement and Communication Plan Update to Deliverable D7.3

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1 Updated Dissemination, Engagement and Communication Plan

2 Abstract/publishable summary

This document provides details on target audiences, goals and tools for disseminating to, engaging with and communicating to a number of selected audiences. The plan summarises the mid-term planned activities for the second 18 months of the project i.e. 1 January 2019-30 June 2020. This plan is going to be regularly updated with the periodic reports due in month 36 and 48.

3 Conclusion & Results

All the work packages in ESIWACE2 have planned to establish processes for dissemination, engagement, communication and for facilitating the exploitation of project results.

- **Engagement with end-users:** The end-users listed in Table 1 of the DoA (Part B) are central to the work done in the project, as they provide with their expert sector knowledge feedback to the project and determine the way in which the project develops. A number of target audiences are addressed by ESIWACE2 work packages: We engage with the weather and climate community in WP6, with the European HPC ecosystem in WP1-6, with the HPC industry in WP2, WP3, and WP6, and with decision and policy makers in WP7.
- **Dissemination** is the public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results) in any medium, including scientific publications. Dissemination of the project results to the weather and climate community is planned in all the WPs but in particular in WP6 through a number of training measures. Dissemination to the European HPC ecosystem is equally shared in all WPs, under the coordination of WP7. The HPC industry is mostly going to be addressed by WP2, WP3, and WP6.
- **Communication** covers three aspects: 1) the internal communication, with tools established for ensuring smooth and timely communications between the project partners and for allowing them to capture and share the project outputs, and also ensuring that the project maintains scientific excellence and all partners remain abreast of new developments in the sector; 2) The communication of the project i.e. strategies for making the project visible; 3) The communication of project results (e.g. dissemination). The promotion of the overall project and its results to the European HPC ecosystem are planned in WP6, but also WP1-5, to decision and policy makers in WP7 and to the public and society at large in WP7. Internal communication within the project is a task of WP7.

Additionally, In order to facilitate dissemination and exploitation, ESIWACE2 complies with the Open Access measures: The Europe H2020 strategy for a smart, sustainable and inclusive economy underlines the central role of knowledge and innovation in generating growth. As stated by the European Commission, "Modern research builds on extensive scientific dialogue and advances by improving earlier work". A full and wide access to scientific publications and data helps to build on previous research results (improved quality of results and improved transparency of the scientific process); fosters collaboration and avoids duplication of effort (greater efficiency); accelerates innovation (faster to market = faster growth). Facilitating exploitation of the project results by the weather and climate community is going to be driven by the training formats implemented in WP6. Exploitation of results by the European HPC ecosystem and the HPC industry is going to be fostered by all the work packages.

4 Detailed report on the deliverable

Target audiences and planned activities

We have identified 6 target audiences. For each audience, we have established objectives, identified relevant messages/contents to be transferred and appropriate tools for transferring these messages during the first 18 months of this project.

4.1 Business sector end-users

We refer here to both emerging and established business end-users.

Thematic area: Weather and climate, HPC, Data science.

Objectives:

- Ensure that direct and indirect users of our services quickly understand the project objectives and potential impacts.
- Ensure project outcomes are relevant and in a useable format.
- Exchange knowledge, ensure maximum benefit.

Workpackage in charge: WP7 coordinates the external communication activities.

Contents/messages: Provide information on services and trainings available, project progress and results, relevant end user documentation, events, literature and/or publications.

Tools:

- Participation in ISC 2019 and ISC 2020 with the project as co-exhibitor of the coordinating institution of the project (DKRZ).
- Sharing of presentations, posters, deliverables in Open Access in Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace>
- Ad hoc sections on services <https://www.esiwace.eu/services>
- Ad hoc section on and trainings <https://www.esiwace.eu/services/trainings>
- Project newsletter: <https://www.esiwace.eu/events-news>
- Project flyer on direct and indirect services.
- Trainings Booklet with the information on the trainings formats.
- Highlights/updates on results/services/trainings on Twitter: <https://twitter.com/esiwace>
- Participation in ICAS 2019.
- Organisation of 6th ENES HPC workshop May 2020 - virtual due to COVID-19

Materials: available in Open Access in Zenodo : <https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace>

4.2 European HPC ecosystem including European and international initiatives and projects

We include in this target audience initiatives and projects such as ETP4HPC, IS-ENES, ExtremeEarth, DYAMOND, EuroHPC, FET and other center of excellence, and the FocusCoE.

Thematic area: Weather and climate, HPC, Data science.

Objectives:

- Exchange knowledge, maximise impact and exploitation, integration of the project with other projects.
- Share resources, ensure synchronisation of activities for addressing open science questions, develop a shared understanding of the project and results, demonstrate the value added through collaborative working. Workpackages in charge: WP6 and WP7.

Tools: Dissemination of project results in several formats (presentations, posters), contribution to the Focus-CoE network and activities, regular publication of scientific findings in open access.

Participation in the following:

- Participation in the quarterly meetings of HPC Task Force.
- Participation in the FocusCoE (CSA) network and contribution to the activities planned by the Focus-CoE. A first meeting was held on 21 February 2019, FocusCoE-CoE workshop, Frankfurt (DE), other meetings are scheduled in the future.
- 16-20 June 2019, ISC 2019, Frankfurt (DE) the project is listed as co-exhibitor.
- 12-14 June 2019, PASC 2019, Zuerich (CH).
- (Participation in PASC 2020): The 2020 event was cancelled due to COVID-19. However, all planned contributions will be transferred to 2021, in particular ESIWACE will again be chairing the mini-symposia on weather and climate.
- Participation in ISC 2020.
- Participation in EuroHPC Summit Week 2019: Input to ETP4HPC SRA4, HPC-Ecosystem Summit.

Organisation of the following:

- CMCC is also organising the “1st European Communities Workshop on Exascale Computing”, that will take place in Poznan (Poland) on May 16th, 2019, during the EuroHPC Summit Week 2019 (13-17 May 2019). This is the first of a series of workshops on Exascale Computing and this year’s focus will be on High Performance Data Analytics.
- Direct interactions with target groups identified in the DoA in WP6 and WP7.
- 6th ENES HPC workshop in May 2020, in Hamburg (DE).

In WP6 we offer training to specific target audiences:

- Training on OASIS3-MCT: the 10-hour on-line course delivered for the first time in July 2020 will be repeated in Spring 2021 and Spring 2022, <https://www.esiwace.eu/services/trainings/training-on-oasis3-mct>
- Training on High Performance Data Analytics (HPDA): the 8-hour on-line course will be delivered three times in October 2020, 2021 and 2022, <https://www.esiwace.eu/services/trainings/training-on-high-performance-data-analytics-hpda>
- Training on Domain Specific Languages (DSL): this training originally planned as a face-to-face workshop, is now planned in September 2020 as an online course because of COVID-19, <https://www.esiwace.eu/services/trainings/training-on-domain-specific-language-dsl>
- The Summer School, planned for August 2020 will be fully virtual because of COVID-19. The next Summer School planned for Summer 2021 will hopefully be in person in Reading. <https://hps.vi4io.org/events/2020/esiwace-school>

- Following up on the very successful *Containerization Hackathon for Modellers* (D2.8), the training on Docker containerisation is being prepared as a live tutorial, followed by hands-on time and step-by-step exercise, and will be presented at the two summer schools.
- The training on C++ for HPC (T2.3) is planned at CSCS in Lugano in fall 2021.
- For the training on IO, material being currently assembled will be presented at the two summer schools.

4.3 National and European governments, policy makers, European Commission services, national services

Thematic areas: Weather and climate, HPC, DGs (RTD, Clima, REGIO, CONNECT). Objectives: Inform HPC policy, provide means for greater understanding of the impact of very high-resolution weather and climate modelling, fostering use of results for policy action. Workpackage in charge: WP7 coordinates the external communication activities.

Tools:

- Ad hoc briefings for this target audience: we are planning a stakeholder meeting in 2019.
- Project factsheet.
- Project flyer on direct and indirect services.
- Trainings Booklet with the information on the trainings formats.
- Highlights/ updates on results/services/trainings on Twitter: <https://twitter.com/esiwace>
- Participation in EuroHPC Summit Week 2019: Input to ETP4HPC SRA4, HPC-Ecosystem Summit.
- Coordinated communication actions targeting the European Commission via FocusCoE.

Materials: available in Open Access in Zenodo : <https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace>

4.4 Higher education course leaders and other research facilities delivering HPC and climate science

Thematic areas: Weather and climate, HPC, Data science.

Objectives: Ensure knowledge is passed on through education, improve the professional skills and competencies of those working in the specific topic areas covered by the project, tackling skills gap of workforce. WP6 plans to offer diverse training programmes on HPC software engineering and more specifically on particular techniques, methods and tools for engineers and scientists in the domain of weather/climate. Attention will be specifically paid to attract female and young people to participate in the training. These trainings constitute a transfer of general knowledge from ESIWACE2 experts to the climate and weather community.

Workpackage in charge: All. Specifically WP6 for training formats.

Tools:

- Participation in the following events:
 - 12-14 June 2019, PASC 2019, Zuerich (CH).
 - Participation in PASC 2020 (postponed to 2021 due to COVID-19).
 - Participation in EGU 2020
 - Participation in EGU 2021: a session on *High resolution modelling of weather and climate* is submitted. Further plans include a splinter meeting for the DYAMOND model intercomparison and a conference booth highlighting ESIWACE2.

- **Organisation of:**

- CERFACS is involved in IS-ENES3, in the organisation of training for OASIS3-MCT. This is a synergy between WP6 in ESIWACE2 and IS-ENES3. Direct interactions with target groups identified in the DoA in WP6 and WP7.
- Co-organisation of the EGU 2019 AS1.6/ CL5.07/ ESS1.5/ OS4.25 Machine learning for Earth System modelling.
- Organisation of 2-5 September 2019, ESIWACE2 Workshop "Machine learning for Weather and Climate Models", Oxford (UK).
- Organisation of the 6th ENES HPC workshop in May 2020 (virtual due to COVID-19).

- **Trainings:** The following trainings formats are suitable to reach out for this audience.

- Training on Domain Specific Languages (DSL) <https://www.esiwace.eu/services/trainings/training-on-domain-specific-language-dsl>
- Training on OASIS3-MCT <https://www.esiwace.eu/services/trainings/training-on-oasis3-mct>
- Training on High Performance Data Analytics (HPDA) <https://www.esiwace.eu/services/trainings/training-on-high-performance-data-analytics-hpda>
- Container Hackathon for Modellers <https://www.esiwace.eu/services/trainings/autum-winter-2019-doc>

- Additional trainings are listed on the website: <https://www.esiwace.eu/services/trainings/>

Materials: available in Open Access in Zenodo : <https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace>

4.5 Public and wider society interested in science projects and results, and/or climate research

Objectives: Ensure the project visibility, raise awareness, achieve visibility for the project and its results through the website, social media and the newsletter.

Workpackage in charge: WP7 coordinates the external communication activities.

Tools:

- Website for visibility of the ESIWACE community www.esiwace.eu
- Public lectures and presentations.
- Press releases and media coverage.
- Quarterly newsletter.
- Twitter account <https://twitter.com/esiwace>

Materials: available in Open Access in Zenodo : <https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace>

4.6 Project partners

Thematic areas: Weather and climate, HPC, Data science.

Objectives: Ensure an effective and integrated project, keep all partners actively involved in the project, timely identify and protect any Intellectual Property.

Workpackage in charge: WP7 coordinates the external communication activities.

- Set up of the intranet (Redmine, see deliverable D7.1), the news system via Atom in the redmine, and mailing lists for each workpackage and for the project as a whole.

- Kickoff meeting sessions on project management, reporting, communication and dissemination: guidelines for the teams on how to disseminate (wiki).
- Monthly teleconferences of the partners including the Coordination, WP leaders and co-leaders, project office representatives.
- Annual meeting for the ESIWACE2 community (one annual meeting in 2019 and one annual meeting in 2020).
- Quarterly reports for each partner on work done, dissemination done, and dissemination planned.
- Quarterly teleconference with entire teams in all the work packages.
- List of the Dissemination records to feed the EU Portal.
- List of the peer-reviewed publications to feed the EU Portal.

WP6 coordinates the trainings on the following formats.

- Training on Domain Specific Languages (DSL): <https://www.esiwace.eu/services/trainings/training-on-domain-specific-language-dsl>
- Training on OASIS3-MCT: <https://www.esiwace.eu/services/trainings/training-on-oasis3-mct>
- Training on High Performance Data Analytics (HPDA): <https://www.esiwace.eu/services/trainings/training-on-high-performance-data-analytics-hpda>
- Docker Container Hackathon for Modellers: <https://www.esiwace.eu/services/trainings/autum-winter-2019-c>
- Additional trainings are listed on the website: <https://www.esiwace.eu/services/trainings/>

Materials: available in Open Access in Zenodo : <https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace>

5 References (Bibliography)

- Annotated Model Grant Agreement, article 38
- The EU Guide to Science Communication
- The 60-minute workout webinar
- The Social media guide for EU funded R&I projects
- IPR helpdesk brochure “Making the Most of Your H2020 Project. Boosting the impact of your project through effective communication, dissemination and exploitation”

6 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

None.

7 How this deliverable contributes to the European strategies for HPC

This deliverable is a preliminary plan including a number of activities for the European HPC community. See in particular the description reported under audience 2).

8 Sustainability

- Synergies are created with the other center of excellence in particular thanks for the work done by the FocusCoE and the inputs provided by ESiWACE2 to the FocusCoE
- We are expecting interesting synergies coming up during the trainings planned in WP6. For example, we collaborate with the HPC Certification Forum¹ to ensure that skills required for climate/weather scientists are represented in the skill tree of the Forum and that delivered material is aligned and integrated. Generated training material is provided as OER material similarly to the HPC carpentry this allows others to reuse and extend it. This sustains the generated training material and our activities.

9 Dissemination, Engagement and Uptake of Results

Target audience As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is the general public.

The general public (PU)

This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience:

We intend to share this plan with FocusCoE and the other CoEs to ensure that we synchronise activities targeting the same audiences.

¹<https://www.hpc-certification.org/>